

2º filtro de seleção

Base: Pubmed

Total de artigos: 43

Artigos incluídos: 25 (CI1=25, CI2=0)

Artigos excluídos: 18 (CE1=13, CE2=3, CE3=0, CE4=2, CE5=0, CE6=0)

ID	Título	Link	Resumo	CI	CE	Motivo da exclusão
003	Leaf: an open-source, model-agnostic, data-driven web application for cohort discovery and translational biomedical research	https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/31592524/	Objective: Academic medical centers and health systems are increasingly challenged with supporting appropriate secondary use of clinical data. Enterprise data warehouses have emerged as central resources for these data, but often require an informatician to extract meaningful information, limiting direct access by end users. To overcome this challenge, we have developed Leaf, a lightweight self-service web application for querying clinical data from heterogeneous data models and sources. Materials and methods: Leaf utilizes a flexible biomedical concept system to define hierarchical concepts and ontologies. Each Leaf concept contains both textual representations and SQL query building blocks, exposed by a simple drag-and-drop user interface. Leaf generates abstract syntax trees which are compiled into dynamic SQL queries. Results: Leaf is a successful production-supported tool at the University of Washington, which hosts a central Leaf instance querying an enterprise data warehouse with over 300 active users. Through the support of UW Medicine (https://uwmedicine.org), the Institute of Translational Health Sciences (https://www.iths.org), and the National Center for Data to Health (https://ctsa.ncats.nih.gov/cd2h/), Leaf source code has been released into the public domain at https://github.com/uwrit/leaf . Discussion: Leaf allows the querying of single or multiple clinical databases simultaneously, even those of different data models. This enables fast installation without costly extraction or duplication. Conclusions: Leaf differs from existing cohort discovery tools because it does not specify a required data model and is designed to seamlessly leverage existing user authentication systems and clinical databases in situ. We believe Leaf to be useful for health system analytics, clinical research data warehouses, precision medicine biobanks, and clinical studies involving large patient cohorts.	CI1		
004	Extending an open-source tool to measure data quality: case report on Observational Health Data Science and Informatics (OHDSI)	https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/32229499/	Introduction: As the health system seeks to leverage large-scale data to inform population outcomes, the informatics community is developing tools for analysing these data. To support data quality assessment within such a tool, we extended the open-source software Observational Health Data Sciences and Informatics (OHDSI) to incorporate new functions useful for population health. Methods: We developed and tested methods to measure the completeness, timeliness and entropy of information. The new data quality methods were applied to over 100 million clinical messages received from emergency department information systems for use in public health syndromic surveillance systems. Discussion: While completeness and entropy methods were implemented by the OHDSI community, timeliness was not adopted as its context did not fit with the existing OHDSI domains. The case report examines the process and reasons for acceptance and rejection of ideas proposed to an open-source community like OHDSI.	CI1		

007	<p>Web Interactive Presentation of EPC Reports: A Foray Into Interactive Reports [Internet]</p>	<p>https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/31503436/</p>	<p>Background: Systematic reviews are consumed by different types of users to address an ever-expanding set of questions and needs. It is unlikely that a single static report will efficiently satisfy the diverse needs of diverse users. It might be practical and satisfactory to give users the ability to generate their own report from the information produced by the systematic review. Methods: We developed an open-source web-based interactive report presentation (IRP) of a systematic review on 14 nonsurgical treatments for Urinary Incontinence (UI) in women. We used data from a systematic review we conducted through the Agency for Healthcare Research and Quality Evidence-based Practice Center Program for the Patient Centered Outcomes Research Institute. We presented wireframes (mockups) of the IRP to a panel of three Duke Health System stakeholders in teleconferences, and incorporated their feedback in the final IR, which includes a visual representation of the evidence base, and allows users to access generic or detailed descriptive and analytic information through a point-and-click interface. Subsequently, the stakeholders piloted the IRP and evaluated its ease of use by answering open ended questions. We proposed a roadmap for scalable IRPs of systematic reviews starting from a thematic analysis of these suggestions. Findings: The final tool (accessible at https://to1.infalliblekitty.com/#index) allows users to obtain descriptive and analytic results for a network of 14 treatment categories, various outcomes (cure, improvement, satisfaction, quality of life) and several subgroups (all women, older women, or those with stress or urge UI). Users can access descriptions overall or for specific sets of studies. The stakeholders were satisfied with the functionality of the tool, and commented on its ease of use. They proposed numerous augmentations, which we organized in themes of presentation (e.g., present information on numbers of trials on figures), analytic (e.g., allow on-the-fly subgroup analyses, explore tradeoffs between several outcomes) and information sharing (e.g., ability to import/export data from/to other software). A roadmap to satisfying these augmentations involves the following: (i) integrating analytic capabilities in the tool, (ii) incorporating ways to assess the tradeoffs between several distinct benefits and harms of interventions with minimal assumptions, (iii) defining an information technology standard for evidence synthesis objects (i.e., what information, in in what format, completely describes an evidence-base and its synthesis), and (iv) developing a rigorous representation of evidence synthesis objects as mathematical graphs that can be analyzed. Conclusions: In sum, we described a foray into an alternative view of a systematic review that complements a static systematic review report. Health system representatives found it useful and practical, and requested analytical, expository, and information sharing augmentations to the tool.</p>	CE4	Relatório técnico.
009	<p>EHDViz: clinical dashboard development using</p>	<p>https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/27013597/</p>	<p>Objective: To design, develop and prototype clinical dashboards to integrate high-frequency health and wellness data streams using interactive and real-time data visualisation and analytics modalities. Materials and methods: We developed a clinical dashboard development framework called electronic healthcare data visualization (EHDViz) toolkit for generating web-based, real-time clinical dashboards for visualising heterogeneous biomedical, healthcare and wellness data. The EHDViz is an</p>	CI1	

	<p>open-source technologies</p>		<p>extensible toolkit that uses R packages for data management, normalisation and producing high-quality visualisations over the web using R/Shiny web server architecture. We have developed use cases to illustrate utility of EHDViz in different scenarios of clinical and wellness setting as a visualisation aid for improving healthcare delivery. Results: Using EHDViz, we prototyped clinical dashboards to demonstrate the contextual versatility of EHDViz toolkit. An outpatient cohort was used to visualise population health management tasks (n=14,221), and an inpatient cohort was used to visualise real-time acuity risk in a clinical unit (n=445), and a quantified-self example using wellness data from a fitness activity monitor worn by a single individual was also discussed (n-of-1). The back-end system retrieves relevant data from data source, populates the main panel of the application and integrates user-defined data features in real-time and renders output using modern web browsers. The visualisation elements can be customised using health features, disease names, procedure names or medical codes to populate the visualisations. The source code of EHDViz and various prototypes developed using EHDViz are available in the public domain at http://ehdviz.dudlevlab.org. Conclusions: Collaborative data visualisations, wellness trend predictions, risk estimation, proactive acuity status monitoring and knowledge of complex disease indicators are essential components of implementing data-driven precision medicine. As an open-source visualisation framework capable of integrating health assessment, EHDViz aims to be a valuable toolkit for rapid design, development and implementation of scalable clinical data visualisation dashboards.</p>		
<p>011</p>	<p>A collaborative learning health system agent-based model: Computational and face validity</p>	<p>https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/34277939/</p>	<p>Introduction: Improving the healthcare system is a major public health challenge. Collaborative learning health systems (CLHS) - network organizations that allow all healthcare stakeholders to collaborate at scale - are a promising response. However, we know little about CLHS mechanisms of actions, nor how to optimize CLHS performance. Agent-based models (ABM) have been used to study a variety of complex systems. We translate the conceptual underpinnings of a CLHS to a computational model and demonstrate initial computational and face validity. Methods: CLHSs are organized to allow stakeholders (patients and families, clinicians, researchers) to collaborate, at scale, in the production and distribution of information, knowledge, and know-how for improvement. We build up a CLHS ABM from a population of patient- and doctor-agents, assign them characteristics, and set them into interaction, resulting in engagement, information, and knowledge to facilitate optimal treatment selection. To assess computational and face validity, we vary a single parameter - the degree to which patients influence other patients - and trace its effects on patient engagement, shared knowledge, and outcomes. Results: The CLHS ABM, developed in Python and using the open-source modeling framework Mesa, is delivered as a web application. The model is simulated on a cloud server and the user interface is a web browser using Python and Plotly Dash. Holding all other parameters steady, when patient influence increases, the overall patient population activation increases, leading to an increase in shared knowledge, and higher median patient outcomes. Conclusions: We present the first theoretically-derived computational model of CLHSs, demonstrating initial computational and face validity. These preliminary results suggest that modeling CLHSs using an ABM is feasible and potentially</p>	<p>CI1</p>	

			valid. A well-developed and validated computational model of the health system may have profound effects on understanding mechanisms of action, potential intervention targets, and ultimately translation to improved outcomes.			
012	Novel open-source electronic medical records system for palliative care in low-resource settings	https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/23941694/	<p>Background: The need for palliative care in sub-Saharan Africa is staggering: this region shoulders over 67% of the global burden of HIV/AIDS and cancer. However, provisions for these essential services remain limited and poorly integrated with national health systems in most nations. Moreover, the evidence base for palliative care in the region remains scarce. This study chronicles the development and evaluation of DataPall, an open-source electronic medical records system that can be used to track patients, manage data, and generate reports for palliative care providers in these settings. DataPall was developed using design criteria encompassing both functional and technical objectives articulated by hospital leaders and palliative care staff at a leading palliative care center in Malawi. The database can be used with computers that run Windows XP SP 2 or newer, and does not require an internet connection for use. Subsequent to its development and implementation in two hospitals, DataPall was tested among both trained and untrained hospital staff populations on the basis of its usability with comparison to existing paper records systems as well as on the speed at which users could perform basic database functions. Additionally, all participants evaluated this program on a standard system usability scale.</p> <p>Results: In a study of health professionals in a Malawian hospital, DataPall enabled palliative care providers to find patients' appointments, on average, in less than half the time required to locate the same record in current paper records. Moreover, participants generated customizable reports documenting patient records and comprehensive reports on providers' activities with little training necessary. Participants affirmed this ease of use on the system usability scale.</p> <p>Conclusions: DataPall is a simple, effective electronic medical records system that can assist in developing an evidence base of clinical data for palliative care in low resource settings. The system is available at no cost, is specifically designed to chronicle care in the region, and is catered to meet the technical needs and user specifications of such facilities.</p>	CI1		
014	Developing Open-Source Models for the US Health System: Practical Experiences and Challenges to Date with the Open-Source Value Project	https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/31392665/	The Innovation and Value Initiative started the Open-Source Value Project with the aim to improve the credibility and relevance of model-based value assessment in the context of the US healthcare environment. As a core activity of the Open-Source Value Project, the Innovation and Value Initiative develops and provides access to flexible open-source economic models that are developed iteratively based on public feedback and input. In this article, we describe our experience to date with the development of two currently released, Open-Source Value Project models, one in rheumatoid arthritis and one in epidermal growth factor receptor-positive non-small-cell lung cancer. We developed both Open-Source Value Project models using the statistical programming language R instead of spreadsheet software (i.e., Excel), which allows the models to capture multiple model structures, model sequential treatment with individual patient simulations, and improve integration with formal evidence synthesis. By developing the models in R, we were also able to use version control systems to manage changes to the source code.	CI1		

			<p>which is needed for iterative and collaborative model development. Similarly, Open-Source Value Project models are freely available to the public to provide maximum transparency and facilitate collaboration. Development of the rheumatoid arthritis and non-small-cell lung cancer model platforms has presented multiple challenges. The development of multiple components of the model platform tailored to different audiences, including web interfaces, required more resources than a cost-effectiveness analysis for a publication would. Furthermore, we faced methodological hurdles, in particular related to the incorporation of multiple competing model structures and novel elements of value. The iterative development based on public feedback also posed some challenges during the review phase, where methodological experts did not always understand feedback from clinicians and vice versa. Response to the Open-Source Value Project by the modeling community and patient organizations has been positive, but feedback from US decision makers has been limited to date. As we progress with this project, we hope to learn more about the feasibility, benefits, and challenges of an open-source and collaborative approach to model development for value assessment.</p>		
015	<p>The International Association for the Study of Lung Cancer Early Lung Imaging Confederation</p>	<p>https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/32027538/</p>	<p>Purpose: To improve outcomes for lung cancer through low-dose computed tomography (LDCT) early lung cancer detection. The International Association for the Study of Lung Cancer is developing the Early Lung Imaging Confederation (ELIC) to serve as an open-source, international, universally accessible environment to analyze large collections of quality-controlled LDCT images and associated biomedical data for research and routine screening care. Methods: ELIC is an international confederation that allows access to efficiently analyze large numbers of high-quality computed tomography (CT) images with associated de-identified clinical information without moving primary imaging/clinical or imaging data from its local or regional site of origin. Rather, ELIC uses a cloud-based infrastructure to distribute analysis tools to the local site of the stored imaging and clinical data, thereby allowing for research and quality studies to proceed in a vendor-neutral, collaborative environment. ELIC's hub-and-spoke architecture will be deployed to permit analysis of CT images and associated data in a secure environment, without any requirement to reveal the data itself (ie, privacy protecting). Identifiable data remain under local control, so the resulting environment complies with national regulations and mitigates against privacy or data disclosure risk. Results: The goal of pilot experiments is to connect image collections of LDCT scans that can be accurately analyzed in a fashion to support a global network using methodologies that can be readily scaled to accrued databases of sufficient size to develop and validate robust quantitative imaging tools. Conclusion: This initiative can rapidly accelerate improvements to the multidisciplinary management of early, curable lung cancer and other major thoracic diseases (eg, coronary artery disease and chronic obstructive pulmonary disease) visualized on a screening LDCT scan. The addition of a facile, quantitative CT scanner image quality conformance process is a unique step toward improving the reliability of clinical decision support with CT screening worldwide.</p>	CE1	<p>Não apresenta o desenvolvimento de um sistema.</p>

016	Development and face validation of ultrasound-guided renal biopsy virtual trainer	https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/32038859/	The overall prevalence of chronic kidney disease in the general population is ~14% with more than 661,000 Americans having a kidney failure. Ultrasound (US)-guided renal biopsy is a critically important tool in the evaluation and management of renal pathologies. This Letter presents KBVTrainer, a virtual simulator that the authors developed to train clinicians to improve procedural skill competence in US-guided renal biopsy. The simulator was built using low-cost hardware components and open source software libraries. They conducted a face validation study with five experts who were either adult/pediatric nephrologists or interventional/diagnostic radiologists. The trainer was rated very highly (>4.4) for the usefulness of the real US images (highest at 4.8), potential usefulness of the trainer in training for needle visualization, tracking, steadiness and hand-eye coordination, and overall promise of the trainer to be useful for training US-guided needle biopsies. The lowest score of 2.4 was received for the look and feel of the US probe and needle compared to clinical practice. The force feedback received a moderate score of 3.0. The clinical experts provided abundant verbal and written subjective feedback and were highly enthusiastic about using the trainer as a valuable tool for future trainees.	CI1		
018	COVID-19 TestNorm: A tool to normalize COVID-19 testing names to LOINC codes	https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/32569358/	Large observational data networks that leverage routine clinical practice data in electronic health records (EHRs) are critical resources for research on coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19). Data normalization is a key challenge for the secondary use of EHRs for COVID-19 research across institutions. In this study, we addressed the challenge of automating the normalization of COVID-19 diagnostic tests, which are critical data elements, but for which controlled terminology terms were published after clinical implementation. We developed a simple but effective rule-based tool called COVID-19 TestNorm to automatically normalize local COVID-19 testing names to standard LOINC (Logical Observation Identifiers Names and Codes) codes. COVID-19 TestNorm was developed and evaluated using 568 test names collected from 8 healthcare systems. Our results show that it could achieve an accuracy of 97.4% on an independent test set. COVID-19 TestNorm is available as an open-source package for developers and as an online Web application for end users (https://clamp.uth.edu/covid/loinc.php). We believe that it will be a useful tool to support secondary use of EHRs for research on COVID-19.	CI1		
021	Designing a medication timeline for patients and physicians	https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/30590550/	Objective: Most electronic health records display historical medication information only in a data table or clinician notes. We designed a medication timeline visualization intended to improve ease of use, speed, and accuracy in the ambulatory care of chronic disease. Materials and methods: We identified information needs for understanding a patient medication history, then applied human factors and interaction design principles to support that process. After research and analysis of existing medication lists and timelines to guide initial requirements, we hosted design workshops with multidisciplinary stakeholders to expand on our initial concepts. Subsequent core team meetings used an iterative user-centered design approach to refine our prototype. Finally, a small pilot evaluation of the design was conducted with practicing physicians. Results: We propose an open-source online prototype that incorporates user feedback from initial design workshops, and broad multidisciplinary audience feedback. We describe the applicable design principles associated with each of the prototype's key features. A pilot evaluation of the design showed improved	CI1		

			<p>physician performance in 5 common medication-related tasks, compared to tabular presentation of the same information. Discussion: There is industry interest in developing medication timelines based on the example prototype concepts. An open, standards-based technology platform could enable developers to create a medication timeline that could be deployable across any compatible health IT application. Conclusion: The design goal was to improve physician understanding of a patient's complex medication history, using a medication timeline visualization. Such a design could reduce temporal and cognitive load on physicians for improved and safer care.</p>			
024	<p>MIRACUM: Medical Informatics in Research and Care in University Medicine</p>	<p>https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/30016814/</p>	<p>Introduction: This article is part of the Focus Theme of Methods of Information in Medicine on the German Medical Informatics Initiative. Similar to other large international data sharing networks (e.g. OHDSI, PCORnet, eMerge, RD-Connect) MIRACUM is a consortium of academic and hospital partners as well as one industrial partner in eight German cities which have joined forces to create interoperable data integration centres (DIC) and make data within those DIC available for innovative new IT solutions in patient care and medical research. Objectives: Sharing data shall be supported by common interoperable tools and services, in order to leverage the power of such data for biomedical discovery and moving towards a learning health system. This paper aims at illustrating the major building blocks and concepts which MIRACUM will apply to achieve this goal. Governance and policies: Besides establishing an efficient governance structure within the MIRACUM consortium (based on the steering board, a central administrative office, the general MIRACUM assembly, six working groups and the international scientific advisory board), defining DIC governance rules and data sharing policies, as well as establishing (at each MIRACUM DIC site, but also for MIRACUM in total) use and access committees are major building blocks for the success of such an endeavor. Architectural framework and methodology: The MIRACUM DIC architecture builds on a comprehensive ecosystem of reusable open source tools (MIRACOLIX), which are linkable and interoperable amongst each other, but also with the existing software environment of the MIRACUM hospitals. Efficient data protection measures, considering patient consent, data harmonization and a MIRACUM metadata repository as well as a common data model are major pillars of this framework. The methodological approach for shared data usage relies on a federated querying and analysis concept. Use cases: MIRACUM aims at proving the value of their DIC with three use cases: IT support for patient recruitment into clinical trials, the development and routine care implementation of a clinico-molecular predictive knowledge tool, and molecular-guided therapy recommendations in molecular tumor boards. Results: Based on the MIRACUM DIC release in the nine months conceptual phase first large scale analysis for stroke and colorectal cancer cohorts have been pursued. Discussion: Beyond all technological challenges successfully applying the MIRACUM tools for the enrichment of our knowledge about diagnostic and therapeutic concepts, thus supporting the concept of a Learning Health System will be crucial for the acceptance and sustainability in the medical community and the MIRACUM university hospitals.</p>	CII		

028	<p>MVSE: An R-package that estimates a climate-driven mosquito-borne viral suitability index</p>	<p>https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/32391139/</p>	<p>Viruses, such as dengue, Zika, yellow fever and chikungunya, depend on mosquitoes for transmission. Their epidemics typically present periodic patterns, linked to the underlying mosquito population dynamics, which are known to be driven by natural climate fluctuations. Understanding how climate dictates the timing and potential of viral transmission is essential for preparedness of public health systems and design of control strategies. While various alternative approaches have been proposed to estimate local transmission potential of such viruses, few open-source, ready to use and freely available software tools exist. We developed the Mosquito-borne Viral Suitability Estimator (MVSE) software package for the R programming environment. MVSE estimates the index P, a novel suitability index based on a climate-driven mathematical expression for the basic reproductive number of mosquito-borne viruses. By accounting for local humidity and temperature, as well as viral, vector and human priors, the index P can be estimated for specific host and viral species in different regions of the globe. We describe the background theory, empirical support and biological interpretation of the index P. Using real-world examples spanning multiple epidemiological contexts, we further demonstrate MVSE's basic functionality, research and educational potentials.</p>	CII		
029	<p>CovidCounties is an interactive real time tracker of the COVID19 pandemic at the level of US counties</p>	<p>https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/33199721/</p>	<p>Management of the COVID-19 pandemic has proven to be a significant challenge to policy makers. This is in large part due to uneven reporting and the absence of open-access visualization tools to present local trends and infer healthcare needs. Here we report the development of CovidCounties.org, an interactive web application that depicts daily disease trends at the level of US counties using time series plots and maps. This application is accompanied by a manually curated dataset that catalogs all major public policy actions made at the state-level, as well as technical validation of the primary data. Finally, the underlying code for the site is also provided as open source, enabling others to validate and learn from this work.</p>	CII		
030	<p>Design and implementation of an affordable, public sector electronic medical record in rural Nepal</p>	<p>https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/28749321/</p>	<p>Introduction: Globally, electronic medical records are central to the infrastructure of modern healthcare systems. Yet the vast majority of electronic medical records have been designed for resource-rich environments and are not feasible in settings of poverty. Here we describe the design and implementation of an electronic medical record at a public sector district hospital in rural Nepal, and its subsequent expansion to an additional public sector facility. Development The electronic medical record was designed to solve for the following elements of public sector healthcare delivery: 1) integration of the systems across inpatient, surgical, outpatient, emergency, laboratory, radiology, and pharmacy sites of care; 2) effective data extraction for impact evaluation and government regulation; 3) optimization for longitudinal care provision and patient tracking; and 4) effectiveness for quality improvement initiatives. Application: For these purposes, we adapted Bahmni, a product built with open-source components for patient tracking, clinical protocols, pharmacy, laboratory, imaging, financial management, and supply logistics. In close partnership with government officials, we deployed the system in February of 2015, added on additional functionality, and iteratively improved the system over the following year. This experience enabled us then to deploy the system at an additional district-level hospital in a different part of the country in under four weeks. We</p>	CII		

			<p>discuss the implementation challenges and the strategies we pursued to build an electronic medical record for the public sector in rural Nepal. Discussion Over the course of 18 months, we were able to develop, deploy and iterate upon the electronic medical record, and then deploy the refined product at an additional facility within only four weeks. Our experience suggests the feasibility of an integrated electronic medical record for public sector care delivery even in settings of rural poverty.</p>			
031	<p>Implementation of an open-source robotic platform for SARS-CoV-2 testing by real-time RT-PCR</p>	<p>https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/34260637/</p>	<p>The current global pandemic due to the SARS-CoV-2 has pushed the limits of global health systems across all aspects of clinical care, including laboratory diagnostics. Supply chain disruptions and rapidly-shifting markets have resulted in flash-scarcity of commercial laboratory reagents; this has motivated health care providers to search for alternative workflows to cope with the international increase in demand for SARS-CoV-2 testing. The aim of this study is to present a reproducible workflow for real time RT-PCR SARS-CoV-2 testing using OT-2 open-source liquid-handling robots (Opentrons, NY). We have developed a framework that includes a code template which is helpful for building different stand-alone robotic stations, capable of performing specific protocols. Such stations can be combined together to create a complex multi-stage workflow, from sample setup to real time RT-PCR. Using our open-source code, it is easy to create new stations or workflows from scratch, adapt existing templates to update the experimental protocols, or to fine-tune the code to fit specific needs. Using this framework, we developed the code for two different workflows and evaluated them using external quality assessment (EQA) samples from the European Molecular Genetics Quality Network (EMQN). The affordability of this platform makes automated SARS-CoV-2 PCR testing accessible for most laboratories and hospitals with qualified bioinformatics personnel. This platform also allows for flexibility, as it is not dependent on any specific commercial kit, and thus it can be quickly adapted to protocol changes, reagent, consumable shortages, or any other temporary material constraints.</p>	CI1		
033	<p>Pediatric-Collaborative Health Outcomes Information Registry (Peds-CHOIR): a learning health system to guide pediatric pain research and treatment</p>	<p>https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/27280328/</p>	<p>The pediatric adaptation of the Collaborative Health Outcomes Information Registry (Peds-CHOIR) is a free, open-source, flexible learning health care system (LHS) that meets the call by the Institute of Medicine for the development of national registries to guide research and precision pain medicine. This report is a technical account of the first application of Peds-CHOIR with 3 aims: (1) to describe the design and implementation process of the LHS; (2) to highlight how the clinical system concurrently cultivates a research platform rich in breadth (eg, clinic characteristics) and depth (eg, unique patient- and caregiver-reporting patterns); and (3) to demonstrate the utility of capturing patient-caregiver dyad data in real time, with dynamic outcomes tracking that informs clinical decisions and delivery of treatments. Technical, financial, and systems-based considerations of Peds-CHOIR are discussed. Cross-sectional retrospective data from patients with chronic pain (N = 352; range, 8-17 years; mean, 13.9 years) and their caregivers are reported, including National Institutes of Health Patient-Reported Outcomes Measurement Information System (PROMIS) domains (mobility, pain interference, fatigue, peer relations, anxiety, and depression) and the Pain Catastrophizing Scale. Consistent with the literature, analyses of initial visits revealed impairments across physical, psychological, and social domains. Patients and caregivers evidenced agreement in observable variables (mobility); however,</p>	CE1	<p>Apresenta o processo envolvido no desenvolvimento do sistema, como o investimento para sua realização. Não descreve o desenvolvimento do sistema</p>	

			caregivers consistently endorsed greater impairment regarding internal experiences (pain interference, fatigue, peer relations, anxiety, and depression) than patients' self-report. A platform like Peds-CHOIR highlights predictors of chronic pain outcomes on a group level and facilitates individually tailored treatment(s). Challenges of implementation and future directions are discussed.			
034	A resource management tool for public health continuity of operations during disasters	https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/24618165/	<p>Objective: We developed and validated a user-centered information system to support the local planning of public health continuity of operations for the Community Health Services Division, Public Health - Seattle & King County, Washington.</p> <p>Methods: The Continuity of Operations Data Analysis (CODA) system was designed as a prototype developed using requirements identified through participatory design. CODA uses open-source software that links personnel contact and licensing information with needed skills and clinic locations for 821 employees at 14 public health clinics in Seattle and King County. Using a web-based interface, CODA can visualize locations of personnel in relationship to clinics to assist clinic managers in allocating public health personnel and resources under dynamic conditions.</p> <p>Results: Based on user input, the CODA prototype was designed as a low-cost, user-friendly system to inventory and manage public health resources. In emergency conditions, the system can run on a stand-alone battery-powered laptop computer. A formative evaluation by managers of multiple public health centers confirmed the prototype design's usefulness. Emergency management administrators also provided positive feedback about the system during a separate demonstration.</p> <p>Conclusions: Validation of the CODA information design prototype by public health managers and emergency management administrators demonstrates the potential usefulness of building a resource management system using open-source technologies and participatory design principles.</p>	CII		
037	Design of the Familial Hypercholesterolaemia Australasia Network Registry: Creating Opportunities for Greater International Collaboration	https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/28344196/	Familial Hypercholesterolemia (FH) is the most common and serious monogenic disorder of lipoprotein metabolism that leads to premature coronary heart disease. There are over 65,000 people estimated to have FH in Australia, but many remain undiagnosed. Patients with FH are often under-treated, but with early detection, cascade family testing and adequate treatment, patient outcomes can improve. Patient registries are key tools for providing new information on FH and enhancing care worldwide. The development and design of the FH Australasia Network Registry is a crucial component in the comprehensive model of care for FH, which aims to provide a standardized, high-quality and cost-effective system of care that is likely to have the highest impact on patient outcomes. Informed by stakeholder engagement, the FH Australasia Network Registry was collaboratively developed by government, patient and clinical networks and research groups. The open-source, web-based Rare Disease Registry Framework was the architecture chosen for this registry owing to its open-source standards, modular design, interoperability, scalability and security features; all these are key components required to meet the ever changing clinical demands across regions. This paper provides a high level blueprint for other countries and jurisdictions to help inform and map out the critical features of an FH registry to meet their particular health system needs.	CEI	Não apresenta o desenvolvimento de um sistema.	

040	<p>A biologically informed method for detecting rare variant associations</p>	<p>https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/27582876/</p>	<p>Background: BioBin is a bioinformatics software package developed to automate the process of binning rare variants into groups for statistical association analysis using a biological knowledge-driven framework. BioBin collapses variants into biological features such as genes, pathways, evolutionary conserved regions (ECRs), protein families, regulatory regions, and others based on user-designated parameters. BioBin provides the infrastructure to create complex and interesting hypotheses in an automated fashion thereby circumventing the necessity for advanced and time consuming scripting. Purpose of the study: In this manuscript, we describe the software package for BioBin, along with type I error and power simulations to demonstrate the strengths and various customizable features and analysis options of this variant binning tool. Results: Simulation testing highlights the utility of BioBin as a fast, comprehensive and expandable tool for the biologically-inspired binning and analysis of low-frequency variants in sequence data. Conclusions and potential implications: The BioBin software package has the capability to transform and streamline the analysis pipelines for researchers analyzing rare variants. This automated bioinformatics tool minimizes the manual effort of creating genomic regions for binning such that time can be spent on the much more interesting task of statistical analyses. This software package is open source and freely available from http://ritchielab.com/software/biobin-download</p>	CII	
042	<p>Improving predictive asthma algorithms with modelled environment data for Scotland: an observational cohort study protocol</p>	<p>https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/29780034/</p>	<p>Introduction: Asthma has a considerable, but potentially, avoidable burden on many populations globally. Scotland has some of the poorest health outcomes from asthma. Although ambient pollution, weather changes and sociodemographic factors have been associated with asthma attacks, it remains unclear whether modelled environment data and geospatial information can improve population-based asthma predictive algorithms. We aim to create the afferent loop of a national learning health system for asthma in Scotland. We will investigate the associations between ambient pollution, meteorological, geospatial and sociodemographic factors and asthma attacks. Methods and analysis: We will develop and implement a secured data governance and linkage framework to incorporate primary care health data, modelled environment data, geospatial population and sociodemographic data. Data from 75 recruited primary care practices (n=500 000 patients) in Scotland will be used. Modelled environment data on key air pollutants at a horizontal resolution of 5 km×5 km at hourly time steps will be generated using the EMEP4UK atmospheric chemistry transport modelling system for the datazones of the primary care practices' populations. Scottish population census and education databases will be incorporated into the linkage framework for analysis. We will then undertake a longitudinal retrospective observational analysis. Asthma outcomes include asthma hospitalisations and oral steroid prescriptions. Using a nested case-control study design, associations between all covariates will be measured using conditional logistic regression to account for the matched design and to identify suitable predictors and potential candidate algorithms for an asthma learning health system in Scotland. Findings from this study will contribute to the development of predictive algorithms for asthma outcomes and be used to form the</p>	CEI	<p>Não apresenta o desenvolvimento de um sistema. Apresenta os estudos preliminares de planeamento para o futuro desenvolvimento.</p>

			<p>basis for our learning health system prototype. Ethics and dissemination: The study received National Health Service Research Ethics Committee approval (16/SS/0130) and also obtained permissions via the Public Benefit and Privacy Panel for Health and Social Care in Scotland to access, collate and use the following data sets: population and housing census for Scotland; Scottish education data via the Scottish Exchange of Data and primary care data from general practice Data Custodians. Analytic code will be made available in the open source GitHub website. The results of this study will be published in international peer reviewed journals.</p>			
043	<p>Real-Time Dissemination of Aggregate Data on Presentation and Outcomes of Patients With Venous Thromboembolism: The RIETE Infographics Project</p>	<p>https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/32936691/</p>	<p>In the current era of patient empowerment and precision medicine, access to timely information is critical to decision-making. Unfortunately, we currently lack patient-specific, real-time data about clinical presentation, risk of thrombotic or hemorrhagic events, key risk factors, and adverse outcomes in patients with venous thromboembolism (VTE). Accordingly, the Registro Informatizado Enfermedad TromboEmbólica (RIETE) investigators developed a tool to provide an open-source, real-time graphic representation of VTE-related data derived from over 90 000 patients with confirmed VTE. This information is intended to facilitate discussion in the informed decision-making process. The current article describes the aims, rationale, methods, and ongoing and future efforts of the real-time VTE infographics developed by the RIETE registry collaborators.</p>		CE1	<p>Não apresenta o desenvolvimento de um sistema.</p>
044	<p>Propagation of program control: a tool for distributed disease surveillance</p>	<p>https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/16621681/</p>	<p>Purpose: The purpose of the study was (1) to identify the requirements for syndromic, disease surveillance and epidemiology systems arising from events such as the SARS outbreak in March 2003, and the deliberate spread of Bacillus anthracis, or anthrax, in the US in 2001; and (2) to use these specifications as input to the construction of a system intended to meet these requirements. An important goal was to provide information about the diffusion of a communicable disease without being dependent on centralised storage of information about individual patients or revealing patient-identifiable information. Methods: The method applied is rooted in the engineering paradigm involving phases of analysis, system specification, design, implementation, and testing. The requirements were established from earlier projects' conclusions and analysis of disease outbreaks. The requirements were validated by a literature study of syndromic and disease surveillance systems. The system was tested on simulated EHR databases generated from microbiology laboratory data. Results: A requirements list that a syndromic and disease surveillance system should meet, and an open source system, "The Snow Agent system", has been developed. The Snow Agent system is a distributed system for monitoring the status of a population's health by distributing processes to, and extracting epidemiological data directly from, the electronic health records (EHR) system in a geographic area. Conclusions: Syndromic and disease surveillance tools should be able to operate at all levels in the health systems and across national borders. Such systems should avoid transferring patient identifiable data, support two-way communications and be able to define and incorporate new and unknown diseases and syndrome definitions that should be reported by the system. The initial tests</p>		CI1	

			of the Snow Agent system shows that it will easily scale to national level in Norway.			
045	Predicting asthma attacks in primary care: protocol for developing a machine learning-based prediction model	https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/31292179/	<p>Introduction: Asthma is a long-term condition with rapid onset worsening of symptoms ('attacks') which can be unpredictable and may prove fatal. Models predicting asthma attacks require high sensitivity to minimise mortality risk, and high specificity to avoid unnecessary prescribing of preventative medications that carry an associated risk of adverse events. We aim to create a risk score to predict asthma attacks in primary care using a statistical learning approach trained on routinely collected electronic health record data. Methods and analysis: We will employ machine-learning classifiers (naïve Bayes, support vector machines, and random forests) to create an asthma attack risk prediction model, using the Asthma Learning Health System (ALHS) study patient registry comprising 500 000 individuals across 75 Scottish general practices, with linked longitudinal primary care prescribing records, primary care Read codes, accident and emergency records, hospital admissions and deaths. Models will be compared on a partition of the dataset reserved for validation, and the final model will be tested in both an unseen partition of the derivation dataset and an external dataset from the Seasonal Influenza Vaccination Effectiveness II (SIVE II) study. Ethics and dissemination: Permissions for the ALHS project were obtained from the South East Scotland Research Ethics Committee 02 [16/SS/0130] and the Public Benefit and Privacy Panel for Health and Social Care (1516-0489). Permissions for the SIVE II project were obtained from the Privacy Advisory Committee (National Services NHS Scotland) [68/14] and the National Research Ethics Committee West Midlands-Edgbaston [15/WM/0035]. The subsequent research paper will be submitted for publication to a peer-reviewed journal and code scripts used for all components of the data cleaning, compiling, and analysis will be made available in the open source GitHub website (https://github.com/hollytibble).</p>		CE1	Não apresenta o desenvolvimento de um sistema. Apresenta a pesquisa que antecede o desenvolvimento.
046	iGAS: A framework for using electronic intraoperative medical records for genomic discovery	https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/28193464/	<p>Objective: Design and implement a HIPAA and Integrating the Healthcare Enterprise (IHE) profile compliant automated pipeline, the integrated Genomics Anesthesia System (iGAS), linking genomic data from the Mount Sinai Health System (MSHS) BioMe biobank to electronic anesthesia records, including physiological data collected during the perioperative period. The resulting repository of multi-dimensional data can be used for precision medicine analysis of physiological readouts, acute medical conditions, and adverse events that can occur during surgery. Materials and methods: A structured pipeline was developed atop our existing anesthesia data warehouse using open-source tools. The pipeline is automated using scheduled tasks. The pipeline runs weekly, and finds and identifies all new and existing anesthetic records for BioMe participants. Results: The pipeline went live in June 2015 with 49.2% (n=15,673) of BioMe participants linked to 40,947 anesthetics. The pipeline runs weekly in minimal time. After eighteen months, an additional 3671 participants were enrolled in BioMe and the number of matched anesthetic records grew 21% to 49,545. Overall percentage of BioMe patients with anesthetics remained similar at 51.1% (n=18,128). Seven patients opted out during this time. The median number of anesthetics per participant was 2 (range 1-144). Collectively, there were over 35 million physiologic data points</p>		CI1	

			and 480,000 medication administrations linked to genomic data. To date, two projects are using the pipeline at MSHS. Conclusion: Automated integration of biobank and anesthetic data sources is feasible and practical. This integration enables large-scale genomic analyses that might inform variable physiological response to anesthetic and surgical stress, and examine genetic factors underlying adverse outcomes during and after surgery.		
049	The Psychometric Properties of a Self-Administered, Open-Source Module for Valuing Metastatic Epidural Spinal Cord Compression Utilities	https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/30178420/	Introduction: Web surveys are often used for utility valuation. Typically, custom utility valuation tools that have not undergone psychometric evaluation are used. Objectives: This study aimed to determine the psychometric properties of a metastatic epidural spinal cord compression (MESCC) module run on a customizable open-source , internet-based, self-directed utility valuation platform (Self-directed Online Assessment of Preferences [SOAP]). Methods: Individuals accompanying patients to the emergency department waiting room in Ottawa, Canada, were recruited. Participants made SOAP MESCC health state valuations in the waiting room and 48 h later at home. Validity, agreement reliability, and responsiveness were measured by logical consistency of responses, smallest detectable change, the interclass correlation coefficient, and Guyatt's responsiveness index, respectively. Results: Of 285 participants who completed utility valuations, only 113 (39.6%) completed the re-test. Of these 113 participants, 92 (81.4%) provided valid responses on the first test and 75 (66.4%) provided valid responses on the test and re-test. Agreement for all groups of health states was adequate, since their smallest detectable change was less than the minimal clinically important difference. The mean interclass correlation coefficients for all health states were > 0.8, indicating at least substantial reliability. Guyatt's responsiveness indices all exceeded 0.80, indicating a high level of responsiveness. Conclusions: To our knowledge, this is the first validated open-source , web-based, self-directed utility valuation module. We have demonstrated the SOAP MESCC module is valid, reproducible, and responsive for obtaining ex ante utilities. Considering the successful psychometric validation of the SOAP MESCC module, other investigators can consider developing modules for other diseases where direct utility valuation is needed.		CEI Não apresenta o desenvolvimento de um sistema.
050	Mosquito habitat and dengue risk potential in Kenya: alternative methods to traditional risk mapping techniques	https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/25545930/	Outbreaks, epidemics and endemic conditions make dengue a disease that has emerged as a major threat in tropical and sub-tropical countries over the past 30 years. Dengue fever creates a growing burden for public health systems and has the potential to affect over 40% of the world population. The problem being investigated is to identify the highest and lowest areas of dengue risk. This paper presents "Similarity Search", a geospatial analysis aimed at identifying these locations within Kenya. Similarity Search develops a risk map by combining environmental susceptibility analysis and geographical information systems, and then compares areas with dengue prevalence to all other locations. Kenya has had outbreaks of dengue during the past 3 years, and we identified areas with the highest susceptibility to dengue infection using bioclimatic variables, elevation and mosquito habitat as input to the model. Comparison of the modelled risk map with the reported dengue epidemic cases obtained from the open source reporting ProMED and Government news reports from 1982-2013 confirmed the high-risk locations that were used as the		CEI Não apresenta o desenvolvimento de um sistema.

			Similarity Search presence cells. Developing the risk model based upon the bioclimatic variables, elevation and mosquito habitat increased the efficiency and effectiveness of the dengue fever risk mapping process.			
052	Role of OpenEHR as an open source solution for the regional modelling of patient data in obstetrics	https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/25900270/	This work investigates, whether openEHR with its reference model, archetypes and templates is suitable for the digital representation of demographic as well as clinical data. Moreover, it elaborates openEHR as a tool for modelling Hospital Information Systems on a regional level based on a national logical infrastructure. OpenEHR is a dual model approach developed for the modelling of Hospital Information Systems enabling semantic interoperability. A holistic solution to this represents the use of dual model based Electronic Healthcare Record systems. Modelling data in the field of obstetrics is a challenge, since different regions demand locally specific information for the process of treatment. Smaller health units in developing countries like Brazil or Malaysia, which until recently handled automatable processes like the storage of sensitive patient data in paper form, start organizational reconstruction processes. This archetype proof-of-concept investigation has tried out some elements of the openEHR methodology in cooperation with a health unit in Colombo, Brazil. Two legal forms provided by the Brazilian Ministry of Health have been analyzed and classified into demographic and clinical data. LinkEHR-Ed editor was used to read, edit and create archetypes. Results show that 33 clinical and demographic concepts, which are necessary to cover data demanded by the Unified National Health System, were identified. Out of the concepts 61% were reused and 39% modified to cover domain requirements. The detailed process of reuse, modification and creation of archetypes is shown. We conclude that, although a major part of demographic and clinical patient data were already represented by existing archetypes, a significant part required major modifications. In this study openEHR proved to be a highly suitable tool in the modelling of complex health data. In combination with LinkEHR-Ed software it offers user-friendly and highly applicable tools, although the complexity built by the vast specifications requires expert networks to define generally excepted clinical models. Finally, this project has pointed out main benefits enclosing high coverage of obstetrics data on the Clinical Knowledge Manager, simple modelling, and wide network and support using openEHR. Moreover, barriers described are enclosing the allocation of clinical content to respective archetypes, as well as stagnant adaption of changes on the Clinical Knowledge Manager leading to redundant efforts in data contribution that need to be addressed in future works.		CEI	Não apresenta o desenvolvimento de um sistema.
054	OpenMRS as an emergency EMR-How we used a global good to create an emergency EMR in a week	https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/33752170/	Background: As the coronavirus pandemic progressed through the United States, Indianapolis Emergency Medical Services (IEMS) identified a gap between the health system capacity and the projected need to support an overwhelmed health care system. In addressing emergencies or special cases, each medical institution in a metropolitan area typically has a siloed process for capturing emergency patient records. These approaches vary in technical capabilities and may include use of an electronic medical record system (EMR) or a hybrid paper/EMR process. Given the projected volume of patients for the COVID-19 pandemic and the proposed multi-institutional team approach needed in case of significant provider illness, IEMS sought a simple, efficient, consolidated EMR solution to support planning for the potential capacity gap. IEMS approached Regenstrief Institute (RI), an		CI1	

			<p>established partner with experience in supporting OpenMRS, a global good EMR platform that had been deployed in multiple settings globally. Objective: The purpose of this project was to determine if OpenMRS, a global good, could be used to quickly stand up a system that would meet the needs for health emergency data collection and reporting. Design and implementation methods: The team used an "all hands on deck" approach, bringing together technical and subject matter experts, and a human-centered and iterative process to ensure the system met the key needs of IEMS. The OpenMRS Reference Application was adapted to the specific need and deployed as Docker containers to servers within the Indiana Health Information Exchange. Project outcomes and lessons learned: In less than two weeks, the Regenstrief team was able to install, configure and set up a working version of OpenMRS to support the desired electronic record requirements for the IEMS disaster field clinics. Using a human-centered approach, the RI team developed, tested, and released a user-friendly, installation-ready solution complete with an end user manual and a base support plan. IEMS and RI are sharing this approach to demonstrate how a global good can quickly generate a solution for COVID-19 and other disaster responses. Conclusions: Open source global goods can rapidly be adapted to meet local needs in an emergency. OpenMRS can be adapted to meet the needs of basic emergency medical services registration, triage, and basic data collection.</p>		
057	<p>Scalable Collaborative Infrastructure for a Learning Healthcare System (SCILHS): architecture</p>	<p>https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/24821734/</p>	<p>We describe the architecture of the Patient Centered Outcomes Research Institute (PCORI) funded Scalable Collaborative Infrastructure for a Learning Healthcare System (SCILHS, http://www.SCILHS.org) clinical data research network, which leverages the \$48 billion dollar federal investment in health information technology (IT) to enable a queryable semantic data model across 10 health systems covering more than 8 million patients, plugging universally into the point of care, generating evidence and discovery, and thereby enabling clinician and patient participation in research during the patient encounter. Central to the success of SCILHS is development of innovative 'apps' to improve PCOR research methods and capacitate point of care functions such as consent, enrollment, randomization, and outreach for patient-reported outcomes. SCILHS adapts and extends an existing national research network formed on an advanced IT infrastructure built with open source, free, modular components.</p>	CE1	<p>Não apresenta o desenvolvimento de um sistema. Apresenta um infraestrutura formada por sistemas.</p>
059	<p>An open source tool to compute measures of inpatient glycemic control: translating from healthcare analytics research to clinical quality improvement</p>	<p>https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/34142017/</p>	<p>Objectives: The objective of this study is to facilitate monitoring of the quality of inpatient glycemic control by providing an open-source tool to compute glucometrics. To allay regulatory and privacy concerns, the tool is usable locally; no data are uploaded to the internet. Materials and methods: We extended code, initially developed for healthcare analytics research, to serve the clinical need for quality monitoring of diabetes. We built an application, with a graphical interface, which can be run locally without any internet connection. Results: We verified that our code produced results identical to prior work in glucometrics. We extended the prior work by including additional metrics and by providing user customizability. The software has been used at an academic healthcare institution. Conclusion: We successfully translated code used for research methods into an open source, user-friendly tool</p>	CI1	

			which hospitals may use to expedite quality measure computation for the management of inpatients with diabetes.			
061	A mobile system for the collection of clinical data and EEG signals by using the sana platform	https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/24851974/	Nowadays, more than 450 millions of people around the world suffer from mental disorders. One of the main problems of that type of illnesses is the lack of early detection, generally due to the reduced number of professionals specialized in mental health, especially in low- and middle-income countries. This article aims at describing the process of construction of an m-Health system that supports the collection of clinical data, including EEG signals, in order to assist the initial assessment of neurologic problems. The system has been mainly developed by using low-cost technology, implemented under the open-source platform SANA, and integrating a non-professional EEG device for the acquisition of bioelectric signals of the brain. The functionalities of this application and its usefulness have been evaluated by a group of six experts who concluded that a) the system implements 100% of the functionalities described in the system design phase, and b) the usefulness of the system's functionalities is 96%.		CE2	Não está disponível gratuitamente.
062	One country's journey to interoperability: Tanzania's experience developing and implementing a national health information exchange	https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/33926428/	Background: Robust, flexible, and integrated health information (HIS) systems are essential to achieving national and international goals in health and development. Such systems are still uncommon in most low and middle income countries. This article describes a first-phase activity in Tanzania to integrate the country's vertical health management information system with the help of an interoperability layer that enables cross-program data exchange. Methods: From 2014 to 2019, the Tanzanian government and partners implemented a five-step procedure based on the "Mind the GAPS" (governance, architecture, program management, and standards) framework and using both proprietary and open-source tools. In collaboration with multiple stakeholders, the team developed the system to address major data challenges via four fully documented "use case scenarios" addressing data exchange among hospitals, between services and the supply chain, across digital data systems, and within the supply chain reporting system. This work included developing the architecture for health system data exchange, putting a middleware interoperability layer in place to facilitate the exchange, and training to support use of the system and the data it generates. Results: Tanzania successfully completed the five-step procedure for all four use cases. Data exchange is currently enabled among 15 separate information systems, and has resulted in improved data availability and significant time savings. The government has adopted the health information exchange within the national strategy for health care information, and the system is being operated and managed by Tanzanian officials. Conclusion: Developing an integrated HIS requires a significant time investment; but ultimately benefit both programs and patients. Tanzania's experience may interest countries that are developing their HIS programs.		CE1	Não apresenta o desenvolvimento de um sistema. Apresenta estratégias para a implementação de interoperabilidade nos sistemas de saúde na Tanzania.
063	An innovative use of instant messaging technology to support a	https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/22559176/	A library service model that provides reference and instructional services by summoning reference librarians from a single service point is described. The system utilizes Libraryh3lp, an open-source, multioperator instant messaging system. The selection and refinement of this solution and technical challenges encountered are explored, as is the design of public services		CE2	Não está disponível integralmente.

	library's single-service point		around this technology, usage of the system, and best practices. This service model, while a major cultural and procedural change at first, is now a routine aspect of customer service for this library.		
064	Void spot assay procedural optimization and software for rapid and objective quantification of rodent voiding function, including overlapping urine spots	https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/29972322/	Mouse urinary behavior is quantifiable and is used to pinpoint mechanisms of voiding dysfunction and evaluate potential human therapies. Approaches to evaluate mouse urinary function vary widely among laboratories, however, complicating cross-study comparisons. Here, we describe development and multi-institutional validation of a new tool for objective, consistent, and rapid analysis of mouse void spot assay (VSA) data. Void Whizzard is a freely available software plugin for FIJI (a distribution of ImageJ) that facilitates VSA image batch processing and data extraction. We describe its features, demonstrate them by evaluating how specific VSA method parameters influence voiding behavior, and establish Void Whizzard as an expedited method for VSA analysis. This study includes control and obese diabetic mice as models of urinary dysfunction to increase rigor and ensure relevance across distinct voiding patterns. In particular, we show that Void Whizzard is an effective tool for quantifying nonconcentric overlapping void spots, which commonly confound analyses. We also show that mouse genetics are consistently more influential than assay design parameters when it comes to VSA outcomes. None of the following procedural modifications to reduce overlapping spots masked these genetic-related differences: reduction of VSA testing duration, water access during the assay period, placement of a wire mesh cage bottom on top of or elevated over the filter paper, treatment of mesh with a hydrophobic spray, and size of wire mesh opening. The Void Whizzard software and rigorous validation of VSA methodological parameters described here advance the goal of standardizing mouse urinary phenotyping for comprehensive urinary phenome analyses.		CE2 Não está disponível integralmente.
065	Engaging older adults in the visualization of sensor data facilitated by an open platform for connected devices	https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/27002473/	Background: The use of smart home sensor systems is growing primarily due to the appeal of unobtrusively monitoring older adult health and wellness. However, integrating large-scale sensor systems within residential settings can be challenging when deployment takes place across multiple environments, requiring customization of applications, connection across various devices and effective visualization of complex longitudinal data. Objective: The objective of the study was to demonstrate the implementation of a smart home system using an open, extensible platform in a real-world setting and develop an application to visualize data real time. Methods: We deployed the open source Lab of Things platform in a house of 11 residents as a demonstration of feasibility over the course of 3 months. The system consisted of Aeon Labs Z-wave Door/Window sensors and an Aeon Labs Multi-sensor that collected data on motion, temperature, luminosity, and humidity. We applied a Rapid Iterative Testing and Evaluation approach towards designing a visualization interface engaging gerontological experts. We then conducted a survey with 19 older adult and caregiver stakeholders to inform further design revisions. Results: Our initial visualization mockups consisted of a bar chart representing activity level over time. Family members felt comfortable using the application. Older adults however, indicated it would be difficult to learn to use the application, and had trouble identifying utility. A key for older adults was ensuring that the data collected could be utilized by their family members, physicians, or caregivers.	CI1	

			<p>Conclusions: The approach described in this work is generalizable towards future smart home deployments and can be a valuable guide for researchers to scale a study across multiple homes and connected devices, and to create personalized interfaces for end users.</p>		
067	<p>Experimental Set Up of P300 Based Brain Computer Interface Using a Bioamplifier and BCI2000 System for Patients with Spinal Cord Injury</p>	<p>https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/26512264/</p>	<p>Objective: Brain computer interface (BCI) is one of the most promising technologies for helping people with neurological disorders. Most current BCI systems are relatively expensive and difficult to set up. Therefore, we developed a P300-based BCI system with a cheap bioamplifier and open source software. The purpose of this study was to describe the setup process of the system and preliminary experimental results. Methods: Ten spinal cord-injured patients were recruited. We used a sixteen-channel EEG(KT88-1016, Contec, China) and BCI2000 software (Wadsworth center, NY, USA). Subjects were asked to spell a 5-character word using the P300-based BCI system with 10 minutes of training. EEG data were acquired during the experiment. After subjects spelled the word for ten trials, the spelling accuracy and information transfer rate (ITR) were obtained in each patient. Results: All subjects performed the experiment without difficulty. The mean accuracy was 59.4±22.8%. The spelling accuracy reversely correlated with the age. Younger subjects spelled with higher accuracy than older subjects (p=0.018). However, sex, injury level, time since injury and ASIA scale were not correlated with the accuracy. The mean of ITR was 2.26±1.22 bit/min. Conclusion: This study showed that a BCI system can be set up inexpensively with a low-price bioamplifier and open-source software. The spelling accuracy was moderately achieved with our system. P300-based BCI is useful in young patients, but modification is necessary in old patients who have low ability of recognition and concentration.</p>	CE1	<p>Não apresenta o desenvolvimento de um sistema. Apresenta a instrumentação de um teste de uma ferramenta</p>
068	<p>An affordable HIV-1 drug resistance monitoring method for resource limited settings</p>	<p>https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/24747156/</p>	<p>HIV-1 drug resistance has the potential to seriously compromise the effectiveness and impact of antiretroviral therapy (ART). As ART programs in sub-Saharan Africa continue to expand, individuals on ART should be closely monitored for the emergence of drug resistance. Surveillance of transmitted drug resistance to track transmission of viral strains already resistant to ART is also critical. Unfortunately, drug resistance testing is still not readily accessible in resource limited settings, because genotyping is expensive and requires sophisticated laboratory and data management infrastructure. An open access genotypic drug resistance monitoring method to manage individuals and assess transmitted drug resistance is described. The method uses free open source software for the interpretation of drug resistance patterns and the generation of individual patient reports. The genotyping protocol has an amplification rate of greater than 95% for plasma samples with a viral load >1,000 HIV-1 RNA copies/ml. The sensitivity decreases significantly for viral loads <1,000 HIV-1 RNA copies/ml. The method described here was validated against a method of HIV-1 drug resistance testing approved by the United States Food and Drug Administration (FDA), the Viroseq genotyping method. Limitations of the method described here include the fact that it is not automated and that it also failed to amplify the circulating recombinant form CRF02_AG from a validation panel of samples, although it amplified subtypes A and B from the same panel.</p>	CE4	<p>Relatório</p>

071	<p>Putting Stakeholder Engagement at the Center of Health Economic Modeling for Health Technology Assessment in the United States</p>	<p>https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/33982198/</p>	<p>While evidence generated from health economic (HE) models is being used more commonly in health technology assessment (HTA) in the US, it is not consistently adopted by different stakeholder groups or across therapeutic areas. We hypothesize that actively engaging with multiple stakeholder groups throughout the model development process may result in models more widely considered by decision makers. To test this hypothesis, the Innovation and Value Initiative has launched a modeling effort to build an open-source HE model focusing on the disease state 'major depressive disorder'. A 20-member advisory group has been formed with representatives from patients, employers, clinicians, innovators, payers, and researchers to guide the model development process. While this effort is still in the early stages, the ongoing stakeholder engagement effort has yielded valuable insights that inform the model design. We have also identified several challenges to implementing this new approach. Our early findings suggest that the stakeholder engagement approach to HE model development has the potential to improve HTA in the US.</p>	CE1	<p>Não apresenta o desenvolvimento de um sistema.</p>
072	<p>Algorithmic Detection of Boolean Logic Errors in Clinical Decision Support Statements</p>	<p>https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/33694144/</p>	<p>Objective: Clinical decision support (CDS) can contribute to quality and safety. Prior work has shown that errors in CDS systems are common and can lead to unintended consequences. Many CDS systems use Boolean logic, which can be difficult for CDS analysts to specify accurately. We set out to determine the prevalence of certain types of Boolean logic errors in CDS statements. Methods: Nine health care organizations extracted Boolean logic statements from their Epic electronic health record (EHR). We developed an open-source software tool, which implemented the Espresso logic minimization algorithm, to identify three classes of logic errors. Results: Participating organizations submitted 260,698 logic statements, of which 44,890 were minimized by Espresso. We found errors in 209 of them. Every participating organization had at least two errors, and all organizations reported that they would act on the feedback. Discussion: An automated algorithm can readily detect specific categories of Boolean CDS logic errors. These errors represent a minority of CDS errors, but very likely require correction to avoid patient safety issues. This process found only a few errors at each site, but the problem appears to be widespread, affecting all participating organizations. Conclusion: Both CDS implementers and EHR vendors should consider implementing similar algorithms as part of the CDS authoring process to reduce the number of errors in their CDS interventions.</p>	CII	
073	<p>Advanced medical imaging protocol workflow-a flexible electronic solution to optimize process efficiency, care quality and patient safety in</p>	<p>https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/23288437/</p>	<p>Radiologists routinely make decisions with only limited information when assigning protocol instructions for the performance of advanced medical imaging examinations. Opportunity exists to simultaneously improve the safety, quality and efficiency of this workflow through the application of an electronic solution leveraging health system resources to provide concise, tailored information and decision support in real-time. Such a system has been developed using an open source, open standards design for use within the Veterans Health Administration. The Radiology Protocol Tool Recorder (RAPTOR) project identified key process attributes as well as inherent weaknesses of paper processes and electronic emulators of paper processes to guide the development of its optimized electronic solution. The design provides a kernel that can be expanded to create an integrated radiology environment. RAPTOR has implications relevant to the greater health care community, and</p>	CII	

	the National VA Enterprise		serves as a case model for modernization of legacy government health information systems.			
075	Chronic patient remote monitoring through the application of big data and internet of things	https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/34256646/	Chronic patients could benefit from the technological advances, but the clinical approaches for this kind of patients are still limited. This paper describes a system for chronic patients monitoring both, in home and external environments. For this purpose, we used novel technologies as big data, cloud computing and internet of things (IoT). Additionally, the system has been validated for three use cases: cardiovascular disease (CVD), hypertension (HPN) and chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD), which were selected for their incidence in the population. This system is innovative within e-health, mainly due to the use of a big data architecture based on open-source components , also it provides a scalable and distributed environment for storage and processing of biomedical sensor data. The proposed system enables the incorporation of non-medical data sources in order to improve the self-management of chronic diseases and to develop better strategies for health interventions for chronic and dependents patients.	CI1		
076	A rigorous algorithm to detect and clean inaccurate adult height records within EHR systems	https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/24734128/	Background: Height is a critical variable for many biomedical analyses because it is an important component of Body Mass Index (BMI). Transforming EHR height measures into meaningful research-ready values is challenging and there is limited information available on methods for "cleaning" these data. Objectives: We sought to develop an algorithm to clean adult height data extracted from EHR using only height values and associated ages. Results: The algorithm we developed is sensitive to normal decreases in adult height associated with aging, is implemented using an open-source software tool and is thus easily modifiable, and is freely available . We checked the performance of our algorithm using data from the Northwestern biobank and a replication sample from the Marshfield Clinic biobank obtained through our participation in the eMERGE consortium. The algorithm identified 1262 erroneous values from a total of 33937 records in the Northwestern sample. Replacing erroneous height values with those identified as correct by the algorithm resulted in meaningful changes in height and BMI records; median change in recorded height after cleaning was 7.6 cm and median change in BMI was 2.9 kg/m(2). Comparison of cleaned EHR height values to observer measured values showed that 94.5% (95% C.I 93.8-% - 95.2%) of cleaned values were within 3.5 cm of observer measured values. Conclusions: Our freely available height algorithm cleans EHR height data with only height and age inputs. Use of this algorithm will benefit groups trying to perform research with height and BMI data extracted from EHR.	CI1		